

Volumetric absorptive microsampling meets electromembrane extraction for the first time: Case example of doxorubicin and its metabolite in whole blood samples

Adam Reguli^a, Hana Bavlovič Piskáčková^a, Olga Lenčová-Popelová^b,
Petra Kollárová-Brázdová^b, Martin Štěrba^b, Stig Pedersen-Bjergaard^{c,d},
Petra Štěrbová-Kovářiková^{a,*}

^a Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry and Pharmaceutical Analysis, Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Králové, Charles University, Akademika Heyrovského 1203, 500 03, Hradec Králové, Czech Republic

^b Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Králové, Charles University, Šimkova 870/13, 500 03, Hradec Králové, Czech Republic

^c Department of Pharmacy, University of Oslo, P.O.Box 1068 Blindern, 0316, Oslo, Norway

^d Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen, Universitetsparken 2, 2100, Copenhagen, Denmark

HIGHLIGHTS

- The first use of electromembrane extraction for VAMS tips treatment.
- Comparison of electromembrane extraction to conventional treatment of VAMS tips.
- Up-to-date anthracyclines assay from whole blood on VAMS tips in non-clinical study.
- Feasible combination of whole blood microsampling and microextraction.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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Background: Microsampling of biological fluids followed by innovative sample pre-treatment reflects trends in bioanalytical chemistry. Volumetric absorptive microsampling (VAMS) enables exact whole blood volume collection and reduces the impact of hematocrit on the assay. In animal studies, it complies with the 3R principles (refine, reduce, replace). It allows for a gentle bleeding technique and a reduction in the number of laboratory animals by enabling ethically acceptable repeated blood collection from a single animal. Treating VAMS tips with

* Corresponding author. Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry and Pharmaceutical Analysis, Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Kralove, Charles University, Akademika Heyrovského 1203, Hradec Kralove, 500 03, Czech Republic.

E-mail address: kovarikova@faf.cuni.cz (P. Štěrbová-Kovářiková).

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Doxorubicinol
Volumetric absorptive microsampling
Electromembrane extraction
Microextraction

electromembrane extraction (EME) in 96-well format offers a smart combination of non-invasive, low-volume blood collection with effective, environmentally friendly sample clean-up.

Results: This study introduces the first application of EME in 96-well format for direct isolation of analytes from 10 μL of whole blood collected onto a VAMS device. Doxorubicin, a clinically used anticancer drug also utilized in cancer/cardio-oncology research involving rodents, where microsampling offers important advantages, and its metabolite doxorubicinol, were selected as relevant analytes. The optimized EME yielded reproducible recoveries for both analytes regardless of hematocrit levels, different anticoagulants, or free multivalent ions in the sample. Compared to conventional VAMS tips treatment, EME reduced matrix effects, increased throughput, and an environmental friendliness of the extraction. The EME followed by the UHPLC-MS/MS assay was validated for both analytes in whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips. The same protocol was implemented to treat plasma to determine the blood-to-plasma ratio of the analytes in the same experiments. The practical utility was demonstrated by analyzing real samples collected from the doxorubicin-treated nude mice.

Significance: The study offers a novel assay combining whole blood microsampling and sample clean-up in microextraction scale for preclinical pharmacokinetic studies with doxorubicin in rodents and for pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic modeling. This advancement in bioanalytical chemistry promotes scalable environmentally friendly procedures compatible with the 3R ethical principles in animal studies. Moreover, the concept of direct VAMS tips treatment with EME may also be easily translatable to clinical settings.

1. Introduction

Miniaturization and simplification of methods enabling high throughput analysis are among the leading trends in recent bioanalytical chemistry [1]. Microsampling of biological fluids, followed by smart sample pre-treatment technique, perfectly fits this concept. In animal studies, microsampling (sample volume $\leq 50 \mu\text{L}$) complies with the 3R principles (i.e., refine, reduce, replace), particularly concerning the refinement and reduction imperative. Collecting microsamples allows for a gentle bleeding technique and a reduction (up to 83 %) in the number of laboratory animals by enabling ethically acceptable repeated blood collection from a single animal, even in small rodents with a low total blood volume [2]. Furthermore, it improves data quality by allowing a description of the complete blood concentration profile from a single animal or by linking therapeutic or toxic effects to drug exposure in individual animals (the pharmacokinetics/pharmacodynamic modelling). Apart from the ethical treatment of animals and the clear advantages for pharmaceutical and medical research, there are also pre-analytical aspects of microsampling, such as simple sample handling, storage, and shipment [3].

Dry blood spot (DBS) is probably the most widely used microsampling technique, predominantly utilized in therapeutic drug monitoring. However, the significant drawback is the impact of hematocrit (HCT) on the assay results and the usual blood volume of 30 μL per spot that may still be too high for repeated sampling in small rodents such as mice. Volumetric absorptive microsampling (VAMS) is a newer technique that significantly eliminates the effect of HCT on the assay [2] and allows for further reduction of the collected sample volume. VAMS devices are composed of a plastic holder with tips made of a unique hydrophilic polymer and are designed for the collection of an exact volume (10, 20 or 30 μL) of blood. The blood drop is obtained by a finger or heel prick in humans and from the tail vein using a needle or dissected soft tail tip in rodents. During collection, the VAMS device is filled by holding the handle at an angle of 45° and dipping the tip into the drop of blood to fill it. Following drying at room temperature (typically for 1–3 h), the device is prepared for storage, transport, or extraction [1]. The analytes are commonly isolated from VAMS tips by direct desorption into an organic solvent (such as methanol or acetonitrile) or water. The extraction is usually enhanced by ultrasonication or agitation. Another technique, such as liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) or elevated temperature desorption can also be employed [1].

Treating blood microsamples with a microextraction technique appears to be a smart solution that combines minimally invasive sample withdrawal, easy sample transport and storage with environmentally friendly sample clean-up, and efficient analyte isolation. Electromembrane extraction (EME) combines principles of liquid-phase microextraction with electrophoresis. The analyte transfer from an

aqueous donor solvent via a supported liquid membrane (SLM), which consists of only a few μL of a water-immiscible organic solvent immobilized on membranes, to an aqueous acceptor solution is accelerated by applying a direct current voltage. EME in low-volume 96-well format provides a promising platform for high-throughput processing of microsamples. EME has been employed to isolate several analytes from various biological samples [4], but it has never been used to extract an analyte from blood absorbed onto VAMS tips. Furthermore, there is also scarce data regarding the extraction of a drug directly from a VAMS device using any miniaturized extraction technique [5].

Doxorubicin (DOX, Fig. S1 A) is the most frequently used anthracycline anticancer drug in clinical practice and it is still indispensable in many current chemotherapeutic protocols. It is also commonly used in different experimental animal *in vivo* models, particularly in cancer research and cardio-oncology. Different mice strains are the most frequently employed species in both these settings. Immunodeficient mice strains, such as athymic nude mice, allow study of the response of xenografted human tumors *in vivo*. However, the pharmacokinetics of DOX can vary among different species and strains, which underlines the importance of quick analysis of its pharmacokinetic profile for a specific species, strain, and dosing regimen. In such studies, VAMS brings the benefit of ethical treatment of animals thanks to less invasive sample collection and repetitive sampling from individual animals, which leads to a reduced number of animals and improved quality of the collected data. Scarce information on the extraction of anthracyclines from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips is available. Only one study presents an assay for DOX and doxorubicinol (DOXol, Fig. S1 A) in whole blood collected from DOX-treated patients at a single and relatively early (40 min) time point after the drug administration to 20 μL VAMS device [6]. The VAMS device has never been used to follow the whole pharmacokinetic profile of anthracyclines in whole blood either in clinical or non-clinical settings. Therefore, an up-to-date, environmentally friendly protocol is needed to assay DOX/DOXol from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips, with clear feasibility for real sample analysis in small rodents, such as mice. The protocol should be suitable for 10 μL volume VAMS tips, to fit for non-clinical experiments in addition to clinical studies and it should provide sufficient sensitivity to allow a description of the elimination phase of the drug pharmacokinetics.

The current paper aims to explore the first single-step desorption and extraction of analytes directly from 10 μL of whole dry blood absorbed onto VAMS tips by applying electromembrane extraction. DOX and its principal metabolite DOXol were selected as relevant model analytes. Furthermore, the same EME protocol has also been implemented to treat plasma allowing estimating the blood-to-plasma ratio of DOX/DOXol in a single experiment. After full method validation, the feasibility of direct treatment of VAMS tips with EME has been proven by analysis of real blood samples taken after administration of DOX to athymic nude mice.

This work has two levels of novelty. Firstly, it presents the first direct treatment of VAMS tips with EME. These experiments were conducted to determine whether EME in the 96-well plate format can effectively isolate drugs from dry whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips without the additional desorption. Secondly, it provides a novel, modern, and fully validated assay with environmentally friendly sample clean-up suitable for preclinical pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic or toxicity studies with DOX in mice.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and materials

Doxorubicin hydrochloride (DOX), doxorubicinol hydrochloride (DOXol), and the internal standards [$^{13}\text{C}, ^2\text{H}_3$]-doxorubicin trifluoroacetate salt ($^{13}\text{C}\text{-d}_3\text{-DOX}$, Fig. S1 B) and [$^{13}\text{C}, ^2\text{H}_3$]-doxorubicinol trifluoroacetate salt ($^{13}\text{C}\text{-d}_3\text{-DOXol}$, Fig. S1 B) were obtained from LGC standards (Lomianki, Poland) and Alsachim (Illkirch, France), respectively. Acetonitrile, methanol, formic acid, acetic acid, ammonium acetate (all LC-MS grade), chloroform, bis(2-ethylhexyl) phosphite (DEHPI), 1-ethyl-2-nitrobenzene (ENB), 2-nitrophenyl pentyl ether (NPPE), 2-undecanone, 1-undecanol and PVDF filters (0.22 μm) were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Milli-Q water was prepared using Millipore purification system (Merck-Millipore, Darmstadt, Germany). The VAMS devices (10 μL ; brand name Mitra $\text{\textcircled{R}}$) were obtained from Trajan Scientific Europe Ltd (Milton Keynes, United Kingdom). Drug-free whole blood and plasma were obtained from the Department of Pharmacology, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Králové, Charles University, from *in vivo* experiments in mice and rabbits approved and supervised by the Animal Welfare Committee of the Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Králové (Charles University, Czech Republic). Whole blood was collected in BD Vacutainer $\text{\textcircled{R}}$ tubes (BD Plymouth, United Kingdom) with potassium ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid salt (EDTA) or lithium heparin (LiHep) in rabbit experiments, and in MiniCollect $\text{\textcircled{R}}$ tubes (Greiner Bio-one, Austria) with LiHep for mice experiments.

2.2. Preparation of solutions

The stock solutions of DOX, DOXol, $^{13}\text{C}\text{-d}_3\text{-DOX}$ and $^{13}\text{C}\text{-d}_3\text{-DOXol}$ (2 mM) were prepared by dissolution of the solid substance in methanol. They were stored at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and were stable within 3 months. Combined or individual DOX and DOXol working solutions (0.05–500 μM) were prepared from the stock solutions by appropriate dilution with methanol and were stable within 1 month while stored at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The 200 mM formic acid and 500 mM acetic acid solutions were prepared by dilution of appropriate volumes of each acid in Milli-Q water. The buffer of pH 3.0 was prepared by mixing 200 mM formic acid with 200 mM ammonium acetate. The acid solutions and buffer were stored at laboratory temperature and utilized within 2 weeks of preparation.

2.3. Preparation of standard, calibration, and QC blood and plasma samples

Fresh drug-free (blank) whole blood from rabbits or mice containing anticoagulants (LiHep or EDTA) was used for the method development and validation. For most of these experiments, rabbit blood was employed due to its accessibility in sufficient volumes without sacrificing the animals, which complies with the 3R approach. Mouse whole blood was then used to validate key aspects of this method for its application in mouse experiments (see Section 2.8). The same procedure applies to the determination of analytes in plasma.

Fresh blank whole blood was spiked with an appropriate amount of working solutions (2 % of the total blood volume) [7]. It was incubated for 20 min at $37\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to reach an equilibrium concentration of analytes between plasma and blood cells. The incubation time and temperature

were selected based on our pilot equilibration and stability experiments (for details, see Supplementary Material – Section 1). Subsequently, the blood was either absorbed onto VAMS tips according to recommendations [1] or frozen and subjected to direct whole blood analysis without VAMS devices later. VAMS tips were dried for 3 h at room temperature and stored in airtight bags with desiccant (10 g, at $8\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) before analysis. All VAMS samples were extracted and analyzed within 2 months. Drug-free (blank) plasma (obtained after blood collection into a LiHep-containing tube) was spiked with an appropriate amount of working solutions, immediately treated, and analyzed.

2.4. Experimental design

A detailed workflow scheme, depicted in Fig. 1, outlines the sequential steps from the development of an extraction procedure to the analysis of samples taken from the real *in vivo* experiments, providing a clear visual representation of the experimental procedures employed in this study.

2.5. Sample treatment

2.5.1. Electromembrane extraction

For the EME, laboratory built 96-well format (previously described [8]) combined with 96-well filter plate with PVDF membranes (pore size 0.45 μm , Millipore Ltd., Carrigtwohill, Ireland) was used. During the extraction, the plate was shaken at Vibramax 100 (Heidolph, Kelheim, Germany). Model ES 0300–0.45 (Delta Elektronika BV, Zierikzee, The Netherlands) was used as the power supply and the current was monitored by a digital multimeter (Volcraft VC 830, Conrade Electronics, Hirschau, Germany).

VAMS tips were dropped into the donor well and the donor solution containing 1 μL of internal standards ($^{13}\text{C}\text{-d}_3\text{-DOX}$ and $^{13}\text{C}\text{-d}_3\text{-DOXol}$, concentration of 2 μM) was added. Then 3 μL of water immiscible organic solvent was dispensed into the outer part of PVDF membranes, attached to the wells of donor plate and acceptor plate was filled with acceptor solution. To initiate the extraction, a voltage was applied (tested range 20–35 V) and the process took 15–25 min while shaken at 850–1050 RPM. The following parameters were optimized during method development: volume (180–235 μL) and composition of donor solution (buffer of pH 3, 200 mM formic acid), composition of supported liquid membrane (DEHPI, NPPE, ENB, 1-undecanol, 2-undecanone and different combinations of these solvents) and volume (50–100 μL) of acceptor solution. The EME procedure was optimized using whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips spiked at a concentration of 100 nM for both analytes.

Furthermore, the EME conditions optimized for VAMS tips treatment were applied to extract the analytes from plasma (25 μL) to enable simultaneous analysis of VAMS tips and plasma.

2.5.2. Conventional method for VAMS tips treatment and its comparison with EME

Various conventional methods for VAMS tips treatment were tested for isolation of DOX and DOXol. VAMS tips, containing whole blood spiked at a concentration of 100 nM for both analytes, were placed into an Eppendorf tube and the following protocols were examined: 1/Fifty μL of water containing IS (with/without the addition of formic acid) were added, samples were sonicated (15 min), precipitated with 200 μL of organic solvent (methanol or acetonitrile) and vortexed (20 s), and 2/ organic solvent with IS was added and sample was sonicated (15 min). Subsequently, all samples were centrifuged (10 000 RPM, 10 min, $4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The resulting supernatant was either filtrated and analyzed or 150 μL of supernatant was evaporated under nitrogen at $40\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, reconstituted to 100 μL of 50 % methanol, filtered and analyzed.

Recoveries from all tested extraction protocols were compared, and the most effective approach was selected for subsequent evaluation of linearity and reproducibility. Recovery, matrix effects, time efficiency,

Fig. 1. The workflow scheme.

and environmental friendliness of the conventional method and EME were compared using spiked whole blood (8.6 and 8600.0 nM for both analytes) absorbed onto VAMS tips.

2.5.3. Sample treatment for direct whole blood analysis without VAMS tips

To test the impact of VAMS device on the assay results, direct analysis of the whole blood collected from the same DOX-administered mice was performed as follows. Fifty μL of the sampled frozen whole blood was spiked with both internal standards and 50 μL of Milli-Q water was mixed and samples were sonicated (30 min). Next, 500 μL of methanol was added and samples were vortexed. After additional sonication (15 min), they were centrifuged (10 000 RPM, 10 min, 4 °C), the supernatant was withdrawn, filtrated, and analyzed.

2.6. UHPLC-MS/MS method

The analysis utilized an Agilent 1290 Infinity LC with Triple Quad LC/MS (6470), incorporating a Jet Stream Electrospray and Mass Hunter software (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Chromatographic conditions were adapted from a previously developed method for anthracycline determination [8]. Briefly, Kinetex C18 (100 \times 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm , Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) column with an identical guard column was maintained at 40 °C. The mobile phase, consisting of 0.0025 % formic acid (A) and acetonitrile with 0.0025 % formic acid (B) was employed in a gradient mode: 0.0–3.0 (20–50 % B), 3.1–4.5 (80 % B), 4.6–6.0 (20 % B). The flow rate was set to 0.35 mL min^{-1} .

Positive ion mode and the following MS settings were used: gas temperature at 300 °C, gas flow of 12 L min^{-1} , sheath gas temperature at 400 °C, sheath gas flow of 12 L min^{-1} , nebulizer at 30 psi, capillary

voltage of 5500 V, and nozzle voltage of 1800 V. Quantification was executed in selected ion monitoring mode with a dwell time of 20 ms. The representative chromatogram together with transitions and collision energies used for quantification are presented in Supplementary material Fig. S1 C and Table S1.

2.7. Pre-validation experiments

In these experiments, the impact of anticoagulants, different blood HCT levels, and presence of chelatable multivalent ions in the sample were tested. These experiments were conducted using a fresh blank whole blood spiked at two concentrations (8.6 nM or 8600 nM) for both analytes. Rabbit blood was used in most of the experiments to adhere to the 3R principle, except for the effect of HCT, where mouse blood was used. Fresh blood was collected into LiHep tubes, except for examining the effect of anticoagulants, where EDTA tubes were also used to collect blood for comparison. After spiking, the whole blood samples were incubated as described in Section 2.3, absorbed onto VAMS tips, dried, extracted using EME, and analyzed. All experiments were performed in 4 replicates.

The impact of anticoagulant was tested using spiked fresh blank whole blood containing two different anticoagulant agents and using real whole blood samples taken from a pilot *in vivo* experiment (DOX administered to rabbits). For spiked samples, fresh whole rabbit blood collected either into LiHep or EDTA tubes was absorbed onto VAMS tips. The determined concentrations of both analytes were compared. For the real whole blood samples, fresh blood was collected from rabbits after administration of DOX (3 mg/kg, *i.v.*) after 6 h when the drug's pharmacokinetics is in the elimination phase. The fresh blood was collected

from the artery either directly onto the VAMS device or into the LiHep or EDTA sampling tubes. After gentle mixing of the sampling tubes, the blood was absorbed onto VAMS tips. The concentrations of both analytes were determined in all these samples and compared.

The effect of HCT was examined using fresh whole mouse blood collected into a LiHep-containing tube at three levels of HCT. Blood samples with different HCT were prepared in-house by centrifugation of blank whole blood (10 min, 750 RPM, 4 °C) and collection of all plasma, followed by dilution of blood cells with plasma to achieve HCT levels of 47.3 %, 57.3 %, and 67.3 %. The selected HCT values reflect the range reported in nude mice of both sexes [9]. Concentrations of both analytes assayed in the whole blood with different HCT absorbed onto VAMS tips were compared.

DOX is well-known to form chelates with multivalent ions [10], which could impact the assay results. Thus, VAMS tips loaded with spiked whole blood were treated with EME using either the developed procedure or with the excess of EDTA, as a strong chelator, added to the donor solution. The concentrations of both analytes determined in samples extracted with and without the addition of EDTA were compared.

2.8. Method validation

The EME method with UHPLC-MS/MS assay for DOX and DOXol in whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips and in plasma was validated following European Medicines Agency (EMA) guidelines [11]. Most of the validation parameters were tested using spiked fresh blank rabbit whole blood (collected into LiHep tubes) and plasma. The suitability of the method for mouse samples was confirmed using spiked fresh blank mouse whole blood (collected into LiHep tubes) and plasma at specific concentration levels. The examined validation parameters included linearity, accuracy, precision, matrix effects, recovery, and stability.

Linearity was tested within the concentration range of 3.5–8600.0 and 1–2600 nM for both DOX and DOXol in whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips and in plasma, respectively. Accuracy and precision (both intra-day and inter-day, $n = 5$ at each level) were gauged at four concentration levels (LLOQ, low QC, medium QC, and high QC) for rabbit whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips and plasma, and at two levels (low QC, high QC) for mouse whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips and plasma. Matrix effects were determined at low and high QC levels for both rabbit and mouse whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips and plasma. Recovery was determined at low and medium QC levels.

The stability of analytes in whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips was tested at two concentration levels (low QC and high QC, $n = 4$). QC VAMS tips allowed to dry at room temperature were analyzed at different times (1, 2, and 3 h) to investigate stability during the drying process. The concentrations assessed after 2 or 3 h were compared to those determined after 1 h of drying, which was the minimum time needed for blood to adequately dry. Long-term stability was evaluated by storing QC VAMS tips either at 8 °C or –80 °C for 2 months.

2.9. In vivo pharmacokinetic study in mice

For the *in vivo* study, female athymic nude mice (8–10 weeks old, $n = 9$) were obtained from Velaz (Czech Republic). The animals were kept under standard housing conditions with free access to water and a standard pellet diet. The study was approved by the Animal Welfare Committee of Charles University, Faculty of Medicine in Hradec Králové.

DOX (5 mg/kg, Teva Pharmaceuticals, Czech Republic) was administered to mice via intravenous injection into the proximal part of the tail vein. Blood drops from each animal ($n = 5$) were collected at 5, 15, 30, 60, 180, 360, and 540 min, and at 24 h post-dose directly onto the VAMS devices after aseptic surgical dissection of the soft tip of the tail (approximately 1–2 mm) under short general anesthesia with isoflurane (1–2%). Buprenorphine (0.1 mg/kg, *s.c.*) was administered for

analgesia. Repeated drop bleeding was enhanced by scab removal and gentle warming of the tail before sampling, while bleeding was immediately stopped with a hemostatic agent (Gelaspon, Chauvin Ankerpharm GmbH) applied with slight pressure. At the end of the experiment, the animals were euthanized by overdose with isoflurane. Whole blood was then immediately collected from the *vena cava inferior* into the LiHep tube. After gentle mixing, the fresh whole blood was absorbed onto VAMS tips or 50 μ L were taken and shock frozen for further analysis, while the rest of the blood was processed to plasma. These experiments were performed to check the possible impact of the VAMS device on the assay results and to determine the blood-to-plasma ratio. In another set of animals ($n = 4$), euthanasia was performed 5 min post-DOX administration with the same blood sampling from the *vena cava* to determine the same parameters close to the C_{\max} of the parent compound (DOX) in plasma.

3. Results and discussion

The VAMS device is designed for blood microsampling, primarily for therapeutic drug monitoring in clinical settings and for preclinical experiments in rodents [2]. Analytes are typically desorbed from VAMS tips using ultrasound or vortex-assisted desorption with an organic solvent or water, commonly followed by an additional sample clean-up step [12]. There is only a single report describing the direct extraction of drugs from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips using a micro-extraction method, namely parallel artificial liquid membrane extraction [5]. Although EME in a 96-well plate format appears to be an optimal solution for the high-throughput processing of microsamples, it has never been used for the isolation of compounds directly from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips.

3.1. Development of EME procedure for isolation of DOX and DOXol from VAMS tips

Before developing the EME procedure, it was essential to establish appropriate conditions for preparing spiked blood samples to allow natural analyte distribution between plasma and blood cells before absorbing onto VAMS tips. Our equilibration study results indicated that 20 min of incubation at 37 °C is optimal to achieve equilibrium for both analytes while minimizing the artificial conversion of DOX to DOXol in the samples (for details, see Supplementary material, Fig. S2).

In the initial EME experiments, we used conditions previously developed for extracting anthracyclines from plasma [8], adjusting only the donor solvent volume to 205 μ L to prevent leakage from the donor well when VAMS tips were inserted. However, applying these conditions to whole blood extraction from VAMS tips resulted in inconsistent analyte recoveries both within and between extractions (Supplementary material, Fig. S3 A) that cannot be improved by simply altering basic extraction conditions (Supplementary material, Fig. S3 B and C). These findings indicate that the plasma extraction protocol is unsuitable for isolating anthracyclines from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips, necessitating further method development specifically for this biological material and the device.

3.1.1. Composition of supported liquid membrane

In the first step of method optimization, we evaluated various organic solvents for preparing the SLM based on literature data and our prior research [8]. We tested DEHPi, NPPE, ENB, and 2-undecanone, which are recommended for analytes with log P values between 1 and 2, encompassing both DOX and DOXol [13,14]. 2-Nitrophenyl octyl ether (NPOE), which is also recommended for this log P range, was found to be ineffective for extracting DOX in previous study [8]. Consequently, it was not tested in this work. Surprisingly, all the tested solvents showed poor recovery, indicating that the presence of whole blood and VAMS tips significantly affects EME efficiency (Fig. 2 A). Next, we examined 1-undecanol individually and in combination with

Fig. 2. Optimization of EME conditions for isolation of DOX/DOXol from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips. Recovery of extraction with different (A) SLM composition, (B) donor phase composition, (C) agitation speed, (D) extraction time, (E) current profiles recorded continuously during three independent extractions and (F) reproducibility of recoveries applying developed extraction protocol. The whole blood was spiked at a concentration of 100 nM before being absorbed onto VAMS tips. The recoveries are expressed as the mean values obtained from four individual experiments \pm SD. ENB – 1-ethyl-2-nitrobenzene, NPPE – 2-nitrophenyl pentyl ether, DHEPi – bis(2-ethylhexyl) phosphite.

the other solvents (1:1, v/v). The theory was that the aromatic properties of one solvent (e.g., ENB) could enhance analyte mass transfer via cation- π interactions, while the aliphatic 1-undecanol could reduce SLM fouling from macromolecules and particles in the biological matrix, increasing recovery [15].

The highest recoveries were obtained using a mixture of ENB and 1-undecanol (1:1, v/v), yielding over 75 % recovery for both analytes

(Fig. 2 A). However, subsequent extractions showed unstable current, suggesting potential SLM leakage. Despite this, we selected this SLM for further optimization.

3.1.2. Optimization of other extraction parameters for enhanced reproducibility

The next step was to optimize the voltage to achieve a stable current

during extraction. We tested voltages from 20 to 35 V, starting at 20 V and increasing to 25 V, 30 V, or 35 V after 1 min. Stability was maintained up to 30 V. Therefore, we settled on starting at 20 V and increasing to 30 V after 1 min, ensuring a stable current for at least 30 min. Although this voltage reduction led to lower recoveries, stable current is crucial for reproducibility. We also found that replacing the donor phase buffer (pH 3) with 200 mM formic acid improved current stability and recovery reproducibility (Fig. 2 B).

Further efforts focused on improving extraction recovery while maintaining the stable current and reproducible extraction. Higher recoveries were achieved when EME plate was shaken at 1050 RPM, but PVDF membrane instability, likely due to the presence of solid VAMS tips, caused occasional dislodging. Thus, we opted for a shaking intensity of 850 RPM despite slightly lower recoveries (Fig. 2 C).

Extraction time was evaluated between 15 and 30 min, with 25 min providing the highest recovery. Longer extraction times showed no significant improvement (Fig. 2 D).

Finally, we optimized the volume of the acceptor solution to minimize sample dilution and enhance assay sensitivity, while ensuring adequate contact between the membrane and acceptor electrode for optimal extraction efficiency. Various volumes of 500 mM acetic acid (50, 75, and 100 μ L) were tested, and 75 μ L were selected as optimal.

After setting up all parameters, the current profile was recorded during 3 independent extractions. The obtained plots show a desirable decreasing current trend and high reproducibility, indicating adequate stability of liquid membrane throughout the entire extraction process [13] (Fig. 2 E) as an essential prerequisite of reproducible extraction. In addition, the developed conditions resulted in reproducible recoveries, both within and between extractions (Fig. 2 F).

The following EME procedure was developed to directly isolate DOX and DOXol from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips: A 10 μ L VAMS tip was immersed in 205 μ L of donor solution containing 200 mM formic acid and 1 μ L of IS. Three μ L of a mixture of ENB with 1-undecanol (1:1, v:v) were utilized as organic solvent for SLM. Each well of the acceptor plate contained 75 μ L of 500 mM acetic acid. The extraction process lasted 25 min with agitation set at 850 RPM. Voltage started at 20 V and was raised to 30 V after 1 min. The same protocol was also applicable for the extraction of both analytes from 25 μ L of plasma which allows for simultaneous analysis of both biological materials.

3.2. Development of conventional extraction method and its comparison with EME

As this was the first use of EME for direct extraction of a drug from the whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips, we also developed a conventional extraction method for comparison. Initially, we explored the desorption of analytes from VAMS tips into methanol, a standard treatment method [1] employed in the study of Harahap et al. [16]. However, in our settings, this yielded poor recoveries. We then tested various desorption solutions and protocols (for details, see Supplementary material, Fig. S4). Comparing recoveries of different protocols, the following procedure was selected as a suitable conventional method for DOX/DOXol isolation from whole blood on VAMS tips: 50 μ L of 0.1 % formic acid in water with IS was added to an Eppendorf tube containing VAMS tip, and the samples were treated in an ultrasonic bath for 15 min. The extract was then precipitated with 200 μ L of acetonitrile, vortexed for 20 s and centrifuged (10 000 RPM, 10 min, 4 $^{\circ}$ C). Subsequently, 150 μ L of supernatant was collected, evaporated, reconstituted into 100 μ L of

Fig. 3. Comparison of the conventional extraction procedure and EME for DOX/DOXol isolation from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips: Comparison of DOX/DOXol extraction with 0.1 % formic acid followed by precipitation with acetonitrile with EME - (A) recovery, (B) normalized matrix effects tested at low (8.6 nM) and high (8600 nM) concentrations, (C) time requirements for treating 20 samples and (D) environmental evaluation using AGREEprep metric tool [17]. The results are expressed as the mean recoveries/matrix effects obtained from 4 individual experiments \pm SD.

50 % methanol, filtrated and analyzed. The linearity of this conventional extraction technique within the concentration range of 3.5–8600.0 nM was tested and yielded $R^2 > 0.999$ (weighting $1/x^2$).

The conventional method showed a moderately higher recovery than EME on both concentrations tested, mainly for DOXol, but at the expense of higher variability of the data on the low-end (Fig. 3 A). On the contrary, EME showed markedly lower matrix effects (Fig. 3 B), which is well in line with the high purification capabilities of EME. Furthermore, calculating the time requirements for extraction of 20 samples revealed

that EME was more than two times faster than the conventional technique (Fig. 3C). Finally, an evaluation of the environmental impact of both methods using the AGREeprep metric tool [17] demonstrated that EME was a more environmentally friendly option (Fig. 3 D). Details of parameters used in the greenness evaluation are presented in the Supplementary material (Table S2 and S3). Based on these comparisons, EME was chosen as the greener and more time-efficient method to be validated and used for the analysis of samples from *in vivo* studies.

Fig. 4. Pre-validation experiments: Concentrations of DOX/DOXol assayed: in fresh whole rabbit blood collected to the LiHep or EDTA tubes spiked at (A) 8.6 nM or (B) 8600 nM concentrations and absorbed onto VAMS tips; (C) in whole blood collected after 6 h post i.v. administration of DOX (3 mg/kg) to rabbits absorbed directly onto VAMS tips or to LiHep or EDTA tubes before absorbed onto VAMS tips; in fresh whole mouse blood with low (47.3 %), medium (57.3 %) and high hematocrit (67.3 %) spiked at either (D) 8.6 nM or (E) 8600 nM concentrations and absorbed onto VAMS tips; and whole blood spiked at (F) 8.6 nM or (G) 8600 nM, absorbed onto VAMS tips, and extracted with and without the addition of EDTA to the donor solution. The results are expressed as the mean concentrations assayed from 4 independent experiments \pm SD. Statistical analysis was performed in GraphPad Prism 10.1.2 using *t*-test corrected for multiple comparison with the Holm-Sidak's method (A, B, F, G) or One-way ANOVA with Bonferroni's multiple comparison test (C, D, E). The level of significance was set on $p \leq 0.05$. ns – not significant.

3.3. Pre-validation experiments

Before full validation, it was necessary to address specific aspects of the DOX assay in whole dry blood microsamples. For the preparation of spiked whole blood samples in this study, fresh blank blood had to be collected into the blood sampling tube with an anticoagulant to prevent clotting. The anticoagulants might bring some bias into the assay of anthracyclines [18]. To examine this, we compared concentrations of the analytes assayed from spiked fresh rabbit whole blood collected to the LiHep or EDTA-containing tubes before being absorbed onto VAMS tips. The results conclusively showed that the choice of anticoagulant for the preparation of spiked samples (calibration and QC samples) did not significantly impact the assay results, as illustrated in Fig. 4 A and 4 B. However, in animal studies, the blood is absorbed onto VAMS tips directly from the blood drop and therefore, no anticoagulant is present in the real samples. To address this, we compared analyte concentrations assayed in fresh whole blood samples taken in different ways after DOX administration (*i.v.*) to rabbits. In each case, the whole animal blood was either absorbed directly onto the VAMS device (*i.e.*, anticoagulant free) or collected in the LiHep or EDTA tubes before absorbing onto VAMS tips. Similar concentrations obtained in all cases (Fig. 4 C) confirm that 1/the presence of anticoagulants is not a significant issue for this method, and 2/both tested anticoagulants can be used when preparing calibration samples.

The VAMS device has been repeatedly proven to absorb the exact blood volume independently of the HCT values, minimizing the variation in the assay results in samples of different HCT [2]. However, some concerns remain with the plausible effect of HCT value on extraction recovery [19]. Thus, we compared concentrations of both analytes in spiked mouse fresh whole blood samples adjusted to three different HCT values – 47.3 %, 57.3 %, and 67.3 %, reflecting the values reported in nude mice in literature [9]. As it is shown in Fig. 4 D and 4 E, no significant differences were found.

The assay from dry whole blood may be affected by anthracyclines' ability to form complexes with multivalent ions [10]. Erythrocyte lysis during sample drying on VAMS tips and subsequent EME makes hemoglobin-derived free iron available for complexation with anthracyclines. To ensure this process does not significantly impact the assay, we performed EME extraction of whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips with and without the addition of EDTA in the donor solution. The addition of EDTA can effectively remove free iron from complexes with anthracyclines [20]. As shown in Fig. 4 F and 4 G, no significant differences in the concentrations of DOX/DOXol were found in samples treated with and without EDTA. This indicates that the complexes are not formed substantially during the drying of whole blood on the VAMS device and subsequent extraction procedure, or they undergo degradation during EME.

3.4. Method validation

The developed EME procedure followed by UHPLC-MS/MS assay of DOX/DOXol in rabbit whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips and rabbit plasma was fully validated following EMA guidelines [11]. The method's suitability for analysis of DOX/DOXol in mouse whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips and mouse plasma was proved by examining selected validation parameters at two concentration levels. Method linearity covered the concentration ranges for both analytes of 3.5–8600.0 nM for whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips and 1–2600 nM for plasma, using weighted standard curves ($1/x^2$), with R^2 values consistently exceeding 0.9996.

IS-normalized matrix effects, intra- and inter-day accuracy, and precision were all within the ± 15 % range specified by the guidelines. Mean extraction recoveries from whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips at 860 nM were 57.0 ± 1.5 % for DOX and 52.7 ± 2.1 % for DOXol. For plasma samples (200 nM), recoveries were 71.2 ± 1.5 % for DOX and 60.5 ± 3.9 % for DOXol. The validation results are presented in Tables 1

and 2.

The stability of analytes in whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips was examined during the drying step (3 h) and long-term storage (at 8 °C and –80 °C in an airtight bag with desiccant for two months), as shown in Table 3. Since less than 6.8 % of the initial amount decomposed, both compounds are sufficiently stable during the tested period. Based on these results, all the VAMS samples were stored at 8 °C and analyzed within 2 months.

3.5. Application of the developed method to the analysis of real samples from *in vivo* pharmacokinetic study

The utility and reliability of the developed method for direct isolation of DOX and DOXol from whole blood collected using VAMS tips, followed by UHPLC-MS/MS analysis, were demonstrated by the analysis of samples from a pharmacokinetic experiment with athymic nude mice. The mice were administered with DOX at the dose (5 mg/kg, *i.v.*), which is clinically relevant and commonly used in preclinical experiments in this species [21]. The concentration-time profile of DOX and DOXol during 24 h post-dose, determined in whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips (10 μ L), is shown in Fig. 5 A. In addition, at 5 min post-dose and at the end of the study (24 h), concentrations of both analytes were also assayed in plasma using the same EME procedure and blood-to-plasma ratio was calculated. Our results show that DOX is quickly and significantly distributed into blood elements after administration, with its concentration at 5 min being considerably higher in whole blood than in plasma. Furthermore, it tends to cumulate herein during the experiment (the whole blood-to-plasma ratio increased from 5.0 at 5 min to 9.2 at 24 h post dose – Fig. 5 B). This finding is in line with literary data [22]. The metabolite's relatively high blood-to-plasma ratio at 5 min likely corresponds with the intracellular metabolism of parent DOX in blood elements. Due to the presence of DOX at a relatively high concentration herein, even its limited conversion to the metabolite can result in a notable increase of DOXol concentration in the whole blood compared to plasma. Compared to DOX, DOXol shows an opposite trend in the whole blood-to-plasma ratio over time, indicating involvement of both efflux of the metabolite and its plasma clearance.

The concentrations of both analytes determined directly in frozen

Table 1
Validation parameters for determination of DOX/DOXol in whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips treated with EME followed by UHPLC-MS/MS assay.

VAMS - Linearity (weight: $1/x^2$)						
Analyte	Range (nM)	R^2	Mean equation $y =$			
DOX	3.5–8600.0	0.9996	0.025540x + 0.010845			
DOXol	3.5–8600.0	0.9997	0.018335x + 0.002821			
Conc. added (nM)	Intra-day		Inter-day		Matrix effects	
	Precision	Accuracy	Precision	Accuracy	IS-normalized	
	R.S.D.	(%)	R.S.D.	(%)	(%)	R.S.D.
						D.
DOX – Rabbit						
3.5	1.4	100.7	2.1	98.2	–	–
10.0	1.5	101.4	0.7	104.1	99.8	1.6
2500.0	2.9	98.3	5.3	95.5	–	–
8000.0	2.1	99.9	2.1	97.6	96.5	0.4
DOX – Mouse						
3.5	1.8	100.9	1.5	103.7	101.4	2.6
8000.0	1.5	101.4	1.5	99.3	96.1	0.1
DOXol – Rabbit						
3.5	3.0	102.2	1.3	100.7	–	–
10.0	1.1	100.7	2.2	103.3	101.2	0.7
2500.0	1.3	100.6	2.8	98.6	–	–
8000.0	1.0	100.1	0.9	99.7	102.3	1.5
DOXol – Mouse						
3.5	1.0	99.0	2.2	101.7	100.7	1.8
8000.0	1.1	101.0	0.7	99.1	102.9	0.6

Table 2
Validation parameters for determination of DOX/DOXol in plasma treated with EME followed by UHPLC-MS/MS assay.

Plasma – Linearity (weight: 1/x ²)						
Analyte	Range (nM)		R ²	Mean equation y =		
DOX	1–2600		0.9998	0.024502x + 0.006476		
DOXol	1–2600		0.9999	0.017412x + 0.006205		
Conc. added (nM)	Intra-day		Inter-day		Matrix effects	
	Precision	Accuracy	Precision	Accuracy	IS-normalized	
	R.S.D.	(%)	R.S.D.	(%)	(%)	R.S. D.
DOX – Rabbit						
1	0.8	99.2	1.2	98.6	–	–
10	1.0	102.4	0.9	106.3	100.8	1.4
200	0.7	97.9	1.0	99.8	–	–
2000	1.0	97.6	0.5	104.1	98.8	1.2
DOX – Mouse						
10	1.1	99.8	0.3	98.9	101.6	1.8
2000	0.2	99.2	0.6	103.8	98.9	0.9
DOXol – Rabbit						
1	0.6	99.3	2.5	101.1	–	–
10	0.4	100.9	1.2	103.4	100.3	1.2
200	0.8	99.1	0.9	98.9	–	–
2000	1.6	98.0	1.2	101.1	98.6	0.8
DOXol – Mouse						
10	0.5	100.1	0.9	98.3	100.4	2.7
2000	2.4	98.9	1.1	101.1	99.5	1.4

whole blood and whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips collected from the same animal were compared (at 5 min and 24 h post-dose) to examine the impact of VAMS device on the assay results. The percentage difference in concentrations of analytes in whole blood absorbed onto VAMS and in frozen whole blood was $\pm 10\%$, which is within the acceptable error of analytical methods. It indicates that the VAMS device has no significant impact on the assay of DOX/DOXol in whole blood (Fig. 5C).

The analyses proved that our EME settings are suitable for analyzing real samples from pharmacokinetic study with DOX in athymic nude mice. In this setting, despite the sampling of a small blood volume (10 μL) EME followed by UHPLC-MS/MS assay is capable of monitoring concentrations of the drug and its main metabolite for 24 h which is a sufficient time for the description of the pharmacokinetic profile of this drug. Compared to other microsampling procedures (DBS, VAMS) followed by conventional extractions of DOX/DOXol in TDM, our protocol allows reaching 1.5–5 times lower LLOQ, despite using lower blood sample volume (i.e., 10 μL for VAMS with EME, instead of 20 or 30 μL used for VAMS and DBS with conventional protocols, respectively). Moreover, the previous studies did not consider aspects related to the

Table 3
Stability of DOX/DOXol in rabbit whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips during. 1/Drying at laboratory temperature for 3 h. The concentrations obtained after 2 or 3 h were compared to the samples analyzed after 1 h of drying (STD), which was the minimal time needed for whole blood to adequately dry. 2/Long-term storage (2 months at 8 or $-80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The concentrations obtained after storing for 2 months were compared to that assayed from freshly prepared VAMS tips (STD). The stability of the analytes was tested at 2 concentrations (10 and 1000 nM) and the results are expressed as a percentage match with STD \pm SD (n = 4).

Stability	Drying at laboratory temperature				Long-term storage					
	Concentration match with STD									
	DOX		DOXol		DOX		DOXol			
	%	S.D.	%	S.D.	%	S.D.	%	S.D.		
10 nM	2 h	105.7	3.6	99.0	6.2	8 $^\circ\text{C}$	96.1	4.1	97.2	2.7
	3 h	104.3	7.9	94.1	6.4	$-80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	99.5	1.6	101.4	0.5
	1000 nM	%	S.D.	%	S.D.	1000 nM	%	S.D.	%	S.D.
2 h	94.2	5.8	96.6	5.6	8 $^\circ\text{C}$	99.8	7.3	100.3	5.9	
3 h	93.2	6.2	96.2	4.7	$-80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	99.7	3.6	101.1	5.0	

analysis of whole blood such as the impact of HCT, anticoagulants, and the ability of ANT to chelate multivalent ions in the sample [16,23]. In addition, our EME-based protocol is applicable to the analysis of DOX/DOXol in mice plasma, allowing for the estimation of the blood-to-plasma ratio in a single analytical procedure. For comparison with previously published methods, see the supplementary material – Table S4.

4. Conclusion

Direct EME was successfully introduced for the first time to analyze the drug and its main metabolite in whole blood microsamples (10 μL) collected onto VAMS device. DOX, the example of the clinically important chemotherapeutic drug often used in preclinical mice experiments, and its metabolite DOXol, served as relevant model analytes. This novel approach integrates two crucial steps – desorption of the analytes from the whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tip and their extraction into the acceptor solution – resulting in fast and efficient analytes isolation and sample clean-up. Our methodology underwent systematic development and optimization specifically for VAMS tips treatment and it was also applicable for extracting DOX and DOXol from small volumes of plasma. This extends the method's practical applicability and allows us to estimate both blood and plasma concentrations for anthracyclines using single approach. The method has been validated according to EMA guidelines. Its practical relevance was verified by the analysis of samples from *in vivo* studies conducted on athymic nude mice, facilitating the determination of the pharmacokinetic profile of DOX and DOXol in individual mice over 24 h.

Our study demonstrates that EME in 96-well format is a suitable microextraction technique for the direct isolation of drugs like anthracyclines from dry whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips. Employing a microextraction method for the treatment of whole blood microsamples collected with a VAMS device represents a promising advancement in bioanalytical chemistry, as it aligns with ongoing efforts to foster environmentally friendly procedures and adopt the 3R principles in animal studies.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Adam Reguli: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Hana Bavlovič Piskáčková:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Olga Lenčová-Popelová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Petra Kollárová-Brázdová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Martin Šterba:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Stig Pedersen-**

Fig. 5. Analysis of samples from *in vivo* pharmacokinetic study. Administration of DOX to athymic nude mice (5 mg/kg, i.v.): (A) Concentration-time profile of DOX/DOXol in whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips (n = 5), (B) blood-to-plasma ratio of DOX/DOXol – 5 min and 24 h post-dose (n = 5) calculated by comparing concentrations of analytes assayed in whole blood absorbed onto VAMS tips (C_{blood}) and plasma (C_{plasma}), (C) difference in concentration of DOX/DOXol determined in whole blood with VAMS device and without VAMS device (direct analysis of the whole blood sample shock-frozen after sampling) at 5 min and 24 h post-dose (n = 4). The results are expressed as mean \pm SD.

Bjergaard: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Petra Štěrbová-Kovářiková:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2024.343459>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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